

Ride 2Rail

**WP4 - DEMONSTRATIONS (PROOF OF
CONCEPTS, TEST AND VALIDATION)**

D4.3 MONITORING TOOLS

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The purpose of this deliverable is to specify the tools and methodologies required to collect and monitor the KPIs necessary for the evaluation of the Ride2Rail demos performance and targets as specified in Section 2.2.1 of the DoA and to be conducted in T5.4. The objective is to clarify how and through what instruments the data will be captured from the project demo sites and then analysed and assessed in the WP5. The tools and the methodologies have been designed based on an iterative process with all the partners involved in the WP (demo sites, CFMs, WP3 and WP5) in order to perfectly understand the constraints of each partner and the limits of the methodologies, to minimize every potential risk and complication (also for the demo participants that will be engaged in the tests), and to increase the attention to the data collected.

First, as defined in D4.2, each KPI has been analysed for understanding the most precise kind of data to collect, its meaning and the way in which it will be used for assessing the impacts and the results of the R2R demos. Then, once the KPIs and their meaning have been assessed, the R2R components, the CFMs applications, and the instruments that will be implemented in each demo site have been studied for understanding their functionalities and the kind of data to produce.

With a clear view of all the systems available and all the all the project needs, it has been possible to match the KPIs with the data available, and so with the tools necessary for collecting the related information.

The document is structured as follows:

- chapter one will report the Background information regarding the Ride2Rail project, the Shift2Rail context, and the purposes of WP4;
- chapter two will describe the KPIs indicated in D4.2 and divided in two groups: the “whole project KPIs” and the “Local KPIs”;
- chapter three will deeper describe the approach and procedure followed for the selection of the tools in the monitoring process;
- chapter four will indicate the different tools and methodologies selected for the collection of data during the demo execution phases
- chapter five will report the conclusions regarding the monitoring process, the expected collection results from the demo sites and some questions still open that will need to be resolved in the project.

Abbreviations and acronyms

CFM	Call For Members
CRM	Customer Relationship Management
CW	Cloud Wallet
D	Deliverable
DC	Driver Companion
DoA	Description of Action
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GHG	Greenhouse Gases
IT	Information Technology
IP	Innovation Programme
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
R2R	Ride2Rail
SERA	Single European Railway Area
S2R	Shift2Rail
T	Task
TC	Travel Companion
WP	Work Package

1. BACKGROUND

1.1. Shift2Rail context

Shift2Rail is the first European rail initiative to seek focused research and innovation and market-driven solutions by accelerating the integration of new and advanced technologies into innovative rail product solutions. Shift2Rail promotes the competitiveness of the European rail industry and meets changing EU transport needs. Research carried out under this Horizon 2020 initiative develops the necessary technology to complete the Single European Railway Area (SERA)

The delivery of Shift2Rail is based around five Innovation Programmes (IPs); the focus of this report is IP4 - IT solutions for attractive rail services. To become a more attractive option, rail must respond to customer needs to support anytime, anywhere, door-to-door, intermodal journeys encompassing distinct modes of transportation. Rail must achieve interoperability with other transport modes and mobility services, with regions, cities and people engaged in social and economic activities, and with the key elements of the supply chains which can make rail products and services available to those people. In order to achieve this, rail needs to take due advantage of the increasing connectivity of people and objects, the availability of European Global Navigation Satellite System-based locations, the advances in cloud computing, big, linked and open data and the propagation of internet and social media. The step towards sharing data needs to be considered and progressively developed, in order to enable service developers to provide connected travellers with the services they need and expect.

1.2. Ride2Rail

A key aspect of delivering more attractive services is by delivering end-to-end (or first- and last-mile) travel services that enable rail as their core mode of mobility. This can be challenging in a rural environment, where connectivity to rail is problematic. It is also relevant in urban or peri-urban environments where there may be poorer provision of public transit.

Contributing to Shift2Rail's IP4, Ride2Rail's overall objective is to develop an innovative framework for intelligent mobility, facilitating the efficient combination of flexible (ride-sharing) and scheduled transport services (rail, bus, and other public transport services), thus enhancing the performance of the overall mobility system. Ride2Rail should, in particular, address the first and last mile problem by offering a wider range of transit options, while harnessing the capacity of single occupancy vehicles, along with existing, or future, demand responsive transit.

Ride2Rail aims to integrate multiple (public/private/social) data sets and existing transport platforms for promoting an effective ride sharing practice of citizens, making it a complementary transport mode that extends public transport networks.

The objectives of the Ride2Rail project are:

- To develop an innovative framework for intelligent mobility, facilitating efficient combination of flexible and scheduled transport services, integrating real-time information about public transport and ride sharing;

- To facilitate the comparison and the choice between multiple options/services classified by a set of criteria, for example environmental, travel time, comfort, cost;
- To encourage carpooling (and ride sharing acceptance) as complementary for public transport;
- To enhance the performance of the overall mobility system, reducing road congestion and environmental impact, reinforcing the mobility offer in rural and low-demand areas;
- To combine travel offer classifications and software components, integrating them into existing collective and on-demand transport services;
- To induct the access to high-capacity services thanks to easy-to-use multimodal and integrated travel planning, booking, ticketing and payment features;
- To design, develop and test in four real demonstrators a set of software components for the IP4 ecosystem, including an enhanced Travel Companion and the crowd-based Transport Service Provider;
- To produce recommendations for replicability.

1.3. Work Package 4 context

Work Package 4 provides the demo context where Ride2Rail will be evaluated. This covers both the contextual factors (such as the types of trips likely to be encountered in a demo area) as well as the capacity for demo site leaders to support evaluation activities, which influences the feasibility of evaluation. The WP4 will implement demonstrations of the project solutions in four locations: Padua (Italy), Athens (Greece); Brno (Czech Republic), Helsinki (Finland). A critical aspect of these demonstrations is to understand their performance against the aims of the project and, in terms of supporting sustainability actions in these locations. It is therefore necessary to specify targets for the expected performance of the Ride2Rail deployment in these locations. These targets are specified as Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). Specifying a complete set of KPIs in a methodical manner allows a full understanding of the impact of RIDE2RAIL, and to define a set of mitigating actions should KPIs not be met during the course of the project. Ultimately, the KPIs will be used to inform the impact analysis for RIDE2RAIL (as calculated in WP5). These impact areas are:

- increase the number of multi-occupancy vehicle trips as opposed to single occupancy-vehicle trips,
- increase access to public transit for users in a rural and/or suburban,
- setting contribute to minimising emissions.

The present document constitutes the Deliverable D4.3 “Monitoring Tools” in the framework of the WP4, task 4.1.

2. KPIS LIST AND DEFINITION

2.1.Scope

A harmonised set of indicators supports a consistent monitoring and measuring approach that can be carried out across the project, thus ensuring the robustness and reliability of the measures. This has been conducted in WP5 T5.1 and reported in D4.2 to feed the preparation of the monitoring tools which are shown in this Deliverable and that will be used in T4.2-4.5.

To achieve this aim, a number of assumptions, objectives and scopes have been specified:

- The scope of the KPIs is to measure the performance associated with the success and the achievements of the R2R solutions.
- The measurement approach is applied to the “whole project” and “local” KPIs as described in D4.2.
- Necessity to review the potential of each KPIs in consideration of a wider opportunity of data and results they can provide.
- Necessity to harmonize and confirm each measuring method and tool with partners in conformity with their capability and to support local measures.
- KPIs need to be based also in consideration of the period and duration of the four demo sites.
- Some KPIs measures need to be able to aggregate across all four demo sites to overall assess the impact of the R2R solutions.
- Out of scope for KPIs are other measures associated with the research impact of Ride2Rail (e.g. associated with dissemination or exploitation).

2.2. Whole project KPIs

As reported in D4.2, “whole project KPIs” are a number of indicators applicable across the entire R2R evaluation with whole project targets.

It is worth to mention that while in the list it is used the term “Ride2Rail App”, in reality there is not a single project app but there are:

- Travel Companion TC app (provided by the CFMs)
- Driver Companion DC app (developed within the Ride2Rail project by the WP3 members)
- Ride2Rail Components (enhancing functionalities of the TC)

Table 1 “Whole project” KPI list (from D4.2)

KPI	DEFINITION
KPI#1 Number of Ride2Rail app users	Demo site users who download the app and request at least one trip
KPI#2 Number of completed Ride2Rail app trips	A completed trip made by a demo site app user
KPI#3 Number of completed multi-occupancy vehicle trips with R2R app	A completed trip made by a demo site app user that involves either rideshare or Robobus (Helsinki)

KPI#4 Number of completed trips involving public transit/rail with R2R app	A completed multi-modal trip
KPI#5 Number of completed commuter trips with R2R app	A completed trip that is a regular journey (work or education) conducted 4 (including outward or return) or more times a week
KPI#6 Number of completed rural trips with R2R app	A complete trip where one or both origin and destination is from a rural (or suburban) location
KPI#7 Number of Ride2Rail app downloads	Number of times app has been downloaded by unique users

2.3. Local KPIs

Local KPIs are indicators relevant only for specific demo sites. These are given only for Athens, Brno, and Helsinki.

Table 2: “Local” KPI list (from D4.2)

KPI	DEFINITION
KPI#A1	Number of parking spaces at urban gate D. Plakentias
KPI#A2	Number of parking spaces at extra-urban Koropi station
KPI#B1	Reduction of need for parking spaces
KPI#B2	Number of surveyed users attracted to R2R app
KPI#H1	Number of walk-in trips with the Robobus

3. APPROACH

The analysis of the potential tools to be used have been carried out with the following approach:

- First, as defined in D4.2, the purpose of each KPI has been analysed for understanding the most precise kind of data to collect and in respect of the planned duration and conditions of the demos in each of the four sites.
- Then, based on the information coming from WP3 and CFMs, the systems that will be used in the R2R demos have been studied in order to understand the best way for exploiting them.
 - o WP3 and CFMs have provided technical specifications about functions and integration issues that will be evaluated in WP5 and that posed technical constraints in terms of the operational aspects of Ride2Rail/Shift2Rail experimentations. While some of these may limit the feasibility of certain measurement methods (e.g. limits on which data are available to access from within Ride2Rail to identify completed trips) other constraints may be useful (e.g. the need to manually install the app means it is easier to identify participating users). All of these elements have been considered for their potential influence in the feasibility of data collection and, when necessary, proper countermeasures have been put in place.
- When none of the three (R2R components, TC, DC) systems can be used for the monitoring purposes of KPIs, it was decided to realize specific surveys to be submitted to users.
 - o The surveys will be realized in partnership with WP5 (Evaluation and Impact assessment) and will be included in the online survey for the usability analysis.
 - o Together with demo site leaders, it was decided to submit surveys to users only at the end of the demo time. The completion of the surveys is the mandatory condition for releasing testers' incentives.

The methodology needs to conform to GDPR generally, and specifically with the data plan specified in D1.3. CFMs have clearly informed the project partners that compliance analysis will be concluded by the end of January 2022 and that from then, if necessary, every countermeasure will be analysed during the prosecution of the project demos.

In order to define a simple and successful measurement methodology that reflects all the constraints and opportunities detected, when possible, it was tried to use a single monitoring approach in order to streamline KPI measurement for demo site partners, for testers, and for analysis of WP5.

The final measurement approach selected reflects the criteria of:

- Reliability → It was built to be consistently able to measure R2R KPIs.
- Feasibility → Built in consideration of limits and technical constraints of the R2R and local demo systems (also about time and participant recruitment limits).
- Lightness → Minimal implementation effort needed for demo partners and minimal participation effort needed for local testers.

As reported previously, an iterative approach was adopted for the selection of the tools. Discussion sessions have been settled with partners of WP3, WP4, WP5 and from CFMs.

Several observations came out during the discussions, and many of them have influenced the final selection for the KPIs measurement. The following list reports these outcomes and related decisions taken:

- WP3 partners noticed that the demos trip data can be linked to anonymous users ID. This means that it is possible to match an anonymous ID user "X" to their trips A, B, C, etc (element relevant to be GDPR compliant).
- CFM partners underlined the impossibility to check if a shared trip has been completed. While trip requests and driver feedbacks are recorded, it is not possible to know if the trip has actually been carried out, taken or completed.
- CFM partners also noticed the impossibility to check if a multimodal journey has really been completed due to the missing of mechanisms (e.g. a token) to follow the access to different means of transports.
- It was noticed the need to avoid the communication of any kind of testers data (neither email address) from TSPs to Ride2Rail partners.
- It was mentioned how some KPIs could need the same source of data. This is a good point because it limits the set of data to be effectively recorded.
- WP5 partners noticed how the monitoring process and the following assessment do not need to be carried out in real time. Indeed, the data can be provided (in csv or JSON format) directly at the end of the demo period.
- It was more than once underlined how the download procedure of R2R apps (the DC and the enhanced TC) can affect the engagement and participation of demo testers. The applications will be available only on Android devices and users will not find them accessing the usual app store. Participants will be contacted and invited by email to download the apps using two specific links (one for the DC and one for the TC). The email will be sent directly by the local demo partners (for being GDPR compliant) and will contain also an appropriate user and installation manual necessary to explain how to remove the Android constraints for apps coming outside the official Google Play store. The advantage of this approach for KPI monitoring is that all participant emails will be known by demo site leaders but, at the same time, this engagement modality can be a barrier due to the complications for installing and using the demo apps.
- The links for acquiring the apps will be prepared by WP4 in order to keep track specifically of the Ride2Rail tester downloads.
- The user manuals will be prepared by the WP3 (for the DC) and by the CFMs (for the TC).
- The local demo sites partners will be in charge for the distributing the Ride2Rail survey links. The survey will be needed for the collection of those KPIs not retrievable by the R2R systems and those data related to demo usability and its overall evaluation.
- It has been decided that local KPIs (for Athens, Helsinki, and Brno) will be recorded directly by the demonstration partners.

3.1. Monitoring tools

As for the considerations expressed above, the initial approach to monitoring tools, which involved the use of questionnaires, reporting and data collection templates, monitoring manuals, has been completely reconsidered. Given the KPIs selected and the Ride2Rail eco-system as service provider, it was decided to proceed towards the simplification of

the data collection procedures. So, two main means of data collecting were proposed: surveys and IT system. Surveys collect information directly from users, demo leaders are responsible to deliver the proper survey link to their site testers. Questionnaire are translated in the language of the demo site. IT System, made by CB TMS and by the Apps Traveler Companion and Driver Companion, for its nature manages data to run services, and so it is an information source to calculate KPIs. This approach deleted the need of reporting and data collection templates and monitoring manuals.

4. MEASUREMENT TOOLS AND SYSTEMS

In order to report in a clear way the strategy adopted for the KPIs measurement and monitoring, a table was settled listing:

- Each KPI title (from D4.2).
- KPI source selected among:
 - o R2R Components
 - o TC
 - o Survey
 - o On site indicator (the data will be collected directly by the demonstration partners).
- KPI description.
- KPI data output (from the Ride2Rail components or from the Shift2Rail ecosystem).
- Survey (if the data coming from the R2R and S2R systems will not be available or enough. The table reports the kind of questions to ask)
- Comments (in case of need to clarify or point out some relevant aspects).

This document provides the information for addressing the systems useful to the KPIs collection during the project demos. The data will be stored completely anonymized in the two IP4 storage areas (the Cloud Wallet - CW - and the Customer Relationship Management - CRM -) and in the Crowd Based TSP system. The information necessary for the post demos monitoring and elaboration will be retrieved and provided in JSON format.

4.1. Monitoring tools – Whole project KPIs

Table 3: Whole project KPIs

KPI	Description	Source	Outputs	Survey	Comments
KPI#1 Number of RIDE2RAIL app users	Demo site users who download the app and request at least one trip	R2RComp	R2R Components store info regarding all the requests received/produced and is able to distinguish the related user IDs (GDPR compliance)	Have you ever used at least once the TC app?	As per the KPI#1 definition, we are not aiming at counting the number of drivers offering trips, then the info available from DC are not usable.
KPI#2 Number of completed RIDE2RAIL app trips	A completed trip made by a demo site app user	TC	Input available in TC. However, we do not have the confirmation that the trip has really been carried/taken	*Ask how many R2R trips a user has completed over the demo period *Ask which type of trip (as passenger, driver, robobus user)	
KPI#3 Number of completed multi-occupancy vehicle trips with R2R app	A completed trip made by a demo site app user that involves either rideshare OR Robobus (Helsinki)	R2RComp	From the Driver Companion (DC) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - completed trip as rideshare - number of passengers in trip 	*How many trips did you take in a ride-share mode? *How many passengers were there in each trip?	
KPI#4 Number of completed trips involving public	A completed multi-modal trip	Survey		*How many trips did you take where your R2R journey then connected with public transit (bus, metro, train)?.	

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transit/rail with R2R app		This connection could be at the before or after the shared journey.	
KPI#5 Number of completed commuter trips with R2R app	A completed trip that is a regular journey (work or education) conducted 4 (including outward or return) or more times a week	Survey	<p>*How many of your trips were commuting from home to work or education?</p> <p>*How many of your trips were commuting from work or education to home?</p>
KPI#6 Number of completed rural trips with R2R app	A complete trip where one or both origin and destination is from a rural (or suburban) location	TC	<p>Extracted from the trip responses stored in the Cloud Wallet.</p> <p>* Did your trips start or end at a rural location (eg XXX [may need to be tailored for each demo site])</p> <p>* May need information from demo sites as to which ODs are in rural or suburban location</p> <p>* Brno and Athens both expect 100% rural trip</p>
KPI#7 Number of Ride2Rail app downloads	Number of times app has been downloaded by unique users	TC/R2RComp	Data will be collected through the counter available within the links to download the apps

4.2. Monitoring tools – Local KPIs

Table 4: Local KPIs

KPI	Source	Outputs	Survey	Comments
KPI#A1 Number of parking spaces at urban gate D. Plakentias	Athens site indicator			Data collected directly by the demonstration partners
KPI#A2 Number of parking spaces at extra-urban Koropi station	Athens site indicator			Data collected directly by the demonstration partners
KPI#B1 Reduction of need for parking spaces	BRNo site indicator			Data collected directly by the demonstration partners
KPI#B2 Number of surveyed users attracted to R2R app	BRNo Survey		* Number of surveyed users in Brno for KPI#2, KPI#4 and KPI#5	
KPI#H1 Number of walk-in trips with the Robobus	Helsinki Survey		* Ask how many walk-in trips with the Robobus a user having downloaded the TC took over in the demo period	

4.3. The surveys

The surveys needed for collecting the missing KPIs data will be shared together with the survey that WP5 is elaborating for the usability of the R2R systems and for the overall evaluation of the demo.

After an internal discussion between WP3, WP4 and WP5, it was determined the impossibility to integrate an in-app survey page within the R2R systems. Consequently, it was decided to use Online Surveys (<https://www.onlinesurveys.ac.uk/>). This tool will be available thanks to the license of UNEW (WP5 leader). It is an Online Survey tool suitable for research and is GDPR compliant.

Demo sites will be in charge to distribute the survey link to their testers. Ideally there will be four different versions of the survey, one for each language of the R2R demo sites. The intention will be to keep the survey as short as possible, in order to incentivize the testers participation and their compliance.

The compilation of the survey will be the only condition for the testers to get access to the project incentives after the demo periods.

4.3.1. Survey mockup

During the analysis of the different alternatives for realising the Ride2Rail monitoring survey, an initial draft survey was realized using the tool Online surveys.

Currently, the mockup is composed by 5 pages/sections: 1- Introduction and consent, 2 - demo selection, 3 - KPI questions, 4 - usability questions, 5 - demographics.

The example pages of the Survey mockup are available in the Appendix and in Deliverable D5.1 (Performance Targets and KPIs).

5. CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable has presented the tools and methodologies for collecting and monitoring the KPIs during the demo phases of the Ride2Rail project, based on the indicators described in D4.2. Having analysed in an iterative process constraints, abilities, and requirements of the demo sites and of the systems developed by the project consortium, the work has adopted the following methodologies for the monitoring.

Data coming from:

- Travel Companion for KPI#2, KPI#6.
- Ride2Rail Components (DC and “TC enhancing components”) for KPI#1, KPI#3.
- TC/R2R Components for KPI#7.
- Survey (exclusively) for KPI#4, KPI#5, KPI#B2, KPI#H1.
- On site indicator for KPI#A1, KPI#A2, KPI#B1.

Due to some technological limits and to some internal constraints of demo partners, not all the necessary data will be collected through the R2R systems, or at least not completely for monitoring purposes. For this reason, the Ride2Rail online survey prepared by the WP5 will include also questions about the missing elements for the KPIs monitoring.

Next step to follow before the demo execution period:

- to clarify the appropriate way for collecting and storing the monitoring data.
- to clarify the user engagement strategies of demo sites for finding the appropriate testers.
- to elaborate and prepare the user and installation manual.
- to finalize the integration phase between CFMs and demo site partners.
- to finalise, together with WP5, the Ride2Rail online surveys.
- to update any KPI monitoring tools based on changes to the technical delivery of Ride2Rail or execution of the demonstrations.

R2R_kpi_survey_draft (copy)

0% complete

Page 1: Introduction page

This page will introduce the survey. It may cover any GDPR type information. Etc etc.

Also might talk about the scope - are we just looking at the app or the whole Ride2Rail experience?

Indicate how long it will take - approximately 5 minutes.

Next >

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R2R_kpi_survey_draft (copy)

20% complete

Page 2: Location

Where did you participate in the Ride2Rail demo?

- Birna
- Padua
- Athens
- Helsinki
- Other

[I have not added yet, but we could have a branch for Helsinki that asks questions in the next page that are more relevant to the Robobus service]

< Previous

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40% complete

Page 3: R2R usage page

How many times have you used the Ride2Rail app as a **passenger** of a shared trip?

How many times have you used the Ride2Rail app as a **driver** of a shared trip?

For all of your Ride2Rail journeys, how many connected to public transit (bus, tram, train, metro) either at the beginning or the end of the trip?

For all of your Ride2Rail journeys, how many were a commute FROM home TO work / education etc?

For all of your Ride2Rail journeys, how many were a commute FROM work / education etc TO home?

For all of your Ride2Rail journeys, how many either started or ended at a rural or suburban location?

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This part of the survey uses a table of questions, [view as separate questions instead?](#)

How would you rate the Ride2Rail app on the following points? By service we mean all the elements of the service - the e-scooter itself, the app, payment, picking up or dropping off the e-scooter, using a helmet etc.

Please don't select more than 1 answer(s) per row.

	Strongly agree	Slightly agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Slightly disagree	Strongly disagree
I think that I would like to use the Ride2Rail app frequently.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I found the Ride2Rail app unnecessarily complex.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I thought the Ride2Rail app was easy to use.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use the Ride2Rail app .	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I found the various functions in the Ride2Rail app were well integrated.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I thought there was too much inconsistency in this Ride2Rail app.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I would imagine that most people would learn to use the Ride2Rail app very quickly.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I found the Ride2Rail app very cumbersome to use.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I felt very confident using the Ride2Rail app.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with the Ride2Rail app.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

What is the best thing about the Ride2Rail app? What did you like about it?

What problems did you face with the Ride2Rail app? What did you dislike about it?

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80% complete

Page 5: About you

How old are you?

- 16 -21
- 22 - 35
- 36 - 51
- 52 - 65
- 65+

What do you do?

- Student
- In work
- Unemployed
- Retired
- Other

What gender do you identify as?

- Female
- Male
- Other
- Prefer not to say

< Previous

Finish ✓

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